

PREDICTING THE PERFORMANCE OF A GRAPH NEURAL NETWORK FOR PARTICLE-FLOW RECONSTRUCTION USING QUANTUM-SVR

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ABSTRACT

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To address the significant increase in data production that CERN’s experiments will face in the coming decades, some traditional algorithms that run on CPUs may be replaced by neural network based algorithms that can easily be accelerated by GPUs. An example of one of these new algorithms is the GNN-based Machine-Learned Particle-Flow (MLPF) algorithm that aims to replace traditional particle-flow algorithm using a data-driven approach. This is a complex model for which it is crucial to achieve the best possible performance. In this report we study the potential of using performance prediction to speed up the hyperparameter optimization process of MLPF. We also study the use of a quantum annealer to train the performance predictor and propose a method to overcome some of the problems derived from the current problem size limitations in quantum systems while increasing the stability of solutions. This allows us to achieve results on a quantum machine comparable to those obtained by a classical regressor, showing how quantum computers could be integrated within the classical ML tuning pipeline.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION	3
2	Performance prediction using classical SVR	4
2.1	Studying the importance of different features	6
2.2	Studying the importance of the training size	8
2.3	Making use of the performance predictor	9
3	Performance prediction using Quantum SVR	10
3.1	Quantum annealing	10
3.2	Using a Quantum SVR	11
3.3	Experiments	12
3.4	QSVR combination	15
4	Conclusions	17
4.1	Further Work	17

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the many possible solutions under investigation to address the significant increase in data production that CERN's experiments face in the coming decades is the replacement of traditional algorithms that run on CPUs by neural network based algorithms that can easily be accelerated by GPUs. The increase in the availability of heterogeneous computing systems also motivates efforts to develop algorithms that can fully utilize GPU hardware. One of these efforts consists of the development of MLPF, a graph neural network with the aim of performing efficient particle flow reconstruction [11], [10].

In order for MLPF to replace the existing rule-based particle flow algorithm (PF), it is crucial that it can make accurate predictions. With the goal of optimizing MLPF's performance, several hyperparameter optimization techniques have been successfully applied [16]. However, the hyperparameter optimization process is very computationally expensive, especially for models that require significant compute resources to train and that have many hyperparameters to optimize, as is the case with MLPF. The main reason why the hyperparameter optimization process is expensive is that usually it is necessary to fully train many different configurations of the model.

In order to alleviate this problem, several algorithms have been proposed such as Successive Halving or Hyperband that implement so called early stopping techniques. The idea behind early stopping is to first train several instances of the model, trials, with different hyperparameter configurations up to a certain number of epochs before terminating the worst performing trials and only continuing to train the most promising ones. One drawback of this method is that learning curves of the model for different configurations may intersect. Therefore, the fact that one specific configuration is better than an other at a certain epoch does not necessarily mean that it is still going to be better a few epochs later.

Another way to address this issue is by using a performance predictor that leverages all the information available from the partial learning curve as well as information from the configuration that generated the curve to predict the final performance of the model. Experts can often detect less promising configurations of a model when looking at their partial learning curves. The idea behind performance prediction in this project is to use a classical regressor, e.g. an SVR, to imitate this behaviour. Thus the goal is for the regressor to predict the final performance of a partially trained model and terminate early the less promising trials [2].

A simple toy example of the potential benefits of using this technique instead of the classical early stopping algorithms can be seen in Figure 1 where a naive plot with two learning curves shows how taking the decision of which configuration should be stopped based on the performance at the last epoch will lead to a less preferable outcome. However, in this same example by looking at the slope of the two learning curves it's easy to detect which one of them will be better at the end.

The work presented in this report consists of a study of the potential of using a simple classical regressor as a performance predictor for MLPF together with a simple proposal of how to use a trained regressor to improve a hyperparameter optimization process. In the final sections, the use of a quantum annealer to train a Quantum-SVR as the performance predictor is studied. Some of the current limitations of this technology are exposed as well as how we managed to deal with them.

Figure 1: Toy example comparing two learning curves showing why, when doing early stopping, using a performance predictor is potentially better than looking at the performance at a certain epoch.

2 Performance prediction using classical SVR

To tackle the performance prediction problem for MLPF it was necessary to choose a regression model that could act as a performance predictor. It is important to note that a requisite for the chosen performance predictor model is that it should not be expensive to train, at least not in comparison with the target model (in this case MLPF). Otherwise, training the predictor could become a bottleneck for the potential resource savings expected from this technique. Keeping that in mind, a classical SVR was chosen as the regressor following an approach similar to the one described in [2]. There are several SVR implementations available, we used the NuSVR implementation from Sklearn [12].

In order to train and evaluate the chosen predictor a dataset with paired up hyperparameter configurations and learning curves was generated. To generate the dataset we first choose the target epoch for the performance prediction as well as the search space of the hyperparameters that will be optimized. For our study, the validation loss at epoch 100 was chosen as the target for the performance predictor along with a search space consisting of seven hyperparameters of different types that can be seen in Table 1. We randomly sampled 300 hyperparameter configurations from the previously mentioned search space and trained MLPF for 100 epochs for each one of them. We used the publicly available Delphes dataset for ML-based particle-flow reconstruction, first introduced in [11] and available at [1]. Following this procedure we generated a dataset with 296 learning curves (see Figure 2) that can be found here [15].

	learning rate	num graph layers id	num graph layers reg	dropout	bin size	output dim	weight decay
type	log uniform	quantized uniform	quantized uniform	uniform	choice	choice	log uniform
range	(1e-6, 3e-2)	[0, 4]	[0, 4]	(0.0, 0.5)	[8, 16, 32, 64, 128]	[8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256]	(1e-6, 1e-1)

Table 1: Hyperparameter search space used to generate the learning curve dataset.

The learning curve dataset was then preprocessed before using it to train and test the NuSVR. This preprocessing consists of removing one outlier with very large training loss and

Figure 2: Insights of MLPF learning curve dataset

scaling the data. For scaling, `MinMaxScaler()` from Sklearn is used on the data for every experiment unless any other is specifically stated.

To train the NuSVR, we always use the loss at the 100th epoch as target but we experiment with including different types of information in the feature vector. As a starting point we define the feature vector in the same way as [2] including the hyperparameters, and information from a fraction of the learning curve. The information from the learning curve consists of the validation loss at each epoch up to a certain point (defined by the known fraction of the learning curve) as well as the first and second order differences of the learning curve.

To evaluate how well the performance predictor works for MLPF we mainly focus on the coefficient of determination R^2 . The R^2 score is defined as one minus the residual sum of squares divided by the total sum of squares: $1 - \frac{SS_{res}}{SS_{tot}}$ and provides a measure of how much of the variation of the target is explained by the prediction model. Therefore the closer the R^2 is to 1 the better. We are interested in seeing how good the predictor is for different fractions of the learning curve as finding the minimum fraction of the learning curve for which the predictor can make acceptable predictions will condition the resource savings of a hyperparameter optimization process that makes use of the predictor.

We perform five fold cross validation on the learning curve dataset for different known fractions of the learning curve. For each fold of the cross validation, 80% of the learning curves are used for training and 20% for validation. For each known fraction of the learning curve we plot the mean R^2 across the five splits as well as the range from the worst to the best R^2 . These results can be seen in Figure 3. As expected, we observe that the R^2 increases when the known fraction of the learning curve increases and furthermore that when 25% of the learning curve is known, the R^2 is already around 0.9. These results are comparable to those presented in [2] even though smaller training sets are used for our experiment. For 25% of the learning curve we also plot the predicted loss vs the true loss for an 8020 traintest split and we highlight that the predictions are quite accurate for the smaller true losses while the higher errors happen for larger true losses which are less relevant for the hyperparameter optimization purposes since those will be early stopped in any case. This plot along with the residual distribution of the losses can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 3: NuSVR R^2 for different known fractions of the learning curve.

Figure 4: Errors of NuSVR predictions for MLPF final loss using 25% of the learning curve

2.1 Studying the importance of different features

As it was described in the previous section the feature vector consists of different information from the configuration and the learning curve. In this section we study the importance of the different pieces of information that contribute to the feature vector.

We begin by studying the importance of each of the different hyperparameters in the search space. Having some insights on which hyperparameters are more relevant for the performance predictor can be useful and might indicate which hyperparameters have a greater impact on MLPF’s performance. This knowledge is useful for any kind of hyperparameter optimization process. We study the importance of each hyperparameter for different known fractions of the learning curves through two approaches. The first one consists on training the NuSVR several times leaving one hyperparameter out of the feature vector each time, we also train the NuSVR without any hyperparameter information in the feature vector. The more the R^2 decreases when leaving one given hyperparameter out, the more relevant that hyperparameter is. The second approach is by making use of the permutation importance score for each hyperparameter, which increases with hyperparameter importance. The results can be seen in Figure 5. Both metrics show that when a large enough known fraction of the learning curve is provided to the predictor the hyperparameters are quite irrelevant for the predictions. This is interesting as

it shows that the performance predictor is actually managing to learn from the learning curves rather than from the configurations. Therefore, it would be interesting to investigate the use of larger search spaces in a future performance prediction hyperparameter optimization process.

Figure 5: Studying the importance of the hyperparameter information on the feature vector

Secondly we study how important the information from the learning curve is. As it was previously introduced, the information from the learning curve consists of a sequence of losses along with its first and second order differences. Therefore, most of the items of the feature vector come from the learning curve information. For instance, with a known fraction of 0.25 the feature vector will have 7 features coming from the configuration, 25 features coming from the learning curve, 24 features coming from the first order differences and 23 features coming from the second order differences. Thus, reducing the information related to the learning curve can help reducing the dimension of the feature space which may be useful to avoid overfitting of SVR models when few training points are used. We study how the R^2 changes when leaving out the finite differences and when using a down-sampled learning curve only including the losses at even epochs (without the finite differences). The results which can be seen in Figure 6, show that using the finite differences can be especially useful for smaller known fractions of the learning curve. However, the differences of the R^2 for the different feature vectors are small and even the R^2 for the down-sampled learning curve could be considered acceptable.

Figure 6: R^2 for different learning curve information used in the feature vector

2.2 Studying the importance of the training size

The importance of the training size for the performance predictor was studied for two main reasons. The first one was to assess if it would be feasible to train the SVR on a Quantum Annealer as the size of the problem that can be solved on the currently available machines of this kind is extremely limited. The second one is that the need for generating a training set to train the performance predictor before hypertuning can start is a drawback. It is therefore interesting to see if it is possible to make good performance predictions without needing the learning curves of many fully trained model configurations.

To assess the importance of the training size we evaluated the model's R^2 for different training sizes using a fixed test size of 148. Using the remaining data, we did five additional train/test splits for each training size for different fractions of the learning curve. The results that can be seen in Figure 7 show that the reduction of the training size has a negative impact on the R^2 . However, for known fractions of the learning curve of 0.25 or larger the mean R^2 is above 0.8 even for 20 training points. Looking at the true vs predicted loss plots (Figure 7) for the different training sizes we see that, for all sizes of the training set, the larger prediction errors happen for large true losses which, as we have previously stated, are less relevant when it comes to the hyperparameter optimization process.

(a) R^2 for different known fractions of lc

(b) True vs predicted test loss

Figure 7: Studying the importance of the training size for MLPF performance predictor

It should be taken into account that having a large feature vector can have a negative impact on the SVR performance when the training size is small. To study this, we compare the R^2 for small training sizes when different feature vectors are used. The results can be seen in Figure 8 and show that indeed for small training sizes it may be beneficial to omit the hyperparameter information from the feature vector. Also in Figure 8, we introduce the QuantileTransformer from Sklearn [12] as a new scaler for preprocessing the data that seems to help the model to perform better than when MinMaxScaler is used, at least for these small training sizes. Another comparison between the two scalers showing this trend can be seen in Figure 9 where we show the model performance for a training size of 50 with using the down-sampled learning curve and hyperparameters as features.

Figure 8: R^2 for different train set sizes and different feature vectors when using QuantileTransformer and MinMaxScaler

Figure 9: Scalers comparison for 50 training size and down-sampled learning curve

2.3 Making use of the performance predictor

Once the predictor has been successfully tested, using it to optimize MLPF hyperparameters is the next natural step. However, production grade frameworks for hyperparameter optimization such as Ray Tune do not currently support the use of performance predictors nor provide any straight forward way to add them into the optimization workflow.

The authors of [2] proposed a relatively complex method to integrate a performance predictor in a hyperparameter optimization workflow whereas we focused on a somewhat simpler approach. Making use of a saved pre-trained performance predictor and having a program that samples random configurations from the hyperparameter search space, partially trains the model for each configuration up to a given epoch, uses the predictor to estimate the final performance for each configuration and lastly finish the training process only for the top n configurations. A diagram representing this simple pipeline can be seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Simple approach to take advantage of performance prediction for hyperparameter optimization using a pre-trained regressor

It is important to notice that the partial training of the random configurations can be done in parallel using for example Ray Core to manage parallel tasks and Ray Cluster to coordinate several nodes on a HPC environment. A first version of this parallel approach was developed and tested for a simpler model as target for the hyperparameter optimization using Flatiron Institute facilities. However this program needs further development in order to be suitable for MLPF and complex models supporting checkpoints and resuming trainings among other features. This is left as future work.

3 Performance prediction using Quantum SVR

Once the accuracy of the performance predictor was assessed using a classical SVR it was decided to try to train the SVR on a quantum computer, specifically on a quantum annealer from D-Wave. Note that we are aware of the current limitations of quantum systems when it comes to the performance and problem size. Therefore, our main goal is not to achieve a better performance compared to a classical SVR, but rather to show how a quantum machine can be used to aid the classical machine learning pipeline and to achieve R^2 scores comparable with those obtained using the Sklearn implementation of the NuSVR. Future work plans include to optimize the QSVR model and training process further with the aim of outperforming classical SVR models.

3.1 Quantum annealing

D-Wave's quantum annealers are specific-purpose quantum computers suitable only for certain optimization and sampling problems. Focusing on optimization, the quantum annealer can solve Ising problems or, equivalently, Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimization problems (QUBO), whose general formulation can be seen in Equation 3.1. These classes of problems can be understood as energy minimization problems. Thus the strategy behind D-Wave's systems is to physically represent the energy minimization problem using the qubits to represent the logical variables of the QUBO. All physical systems tend to their minimum energy state, thus, after some amount of time the qubits will, with high likelihood, be in a state that represents a global minimum of the objective function [7].

$$\text{Minimize: } f(x) = \sum_{i < j}^N Q_{i,j} x_i x_j + \sum_i^N Q_{i,i} x_i \quad (3.1)$$

Where: $x_i \in \{0, 1\}$ and Q is a $N \times N$ symmetric matrix

It is important to note that when using the quantum annealer, the process of starting at a superposition state and evolving to a minimum energy state is probabilistic and therefore it is repeated several times. Hence, the quantum annealer provides several solutions for the problem with the most repeated solutions being the most likely to be the actual solution of the problem.

3.2 Using a Quantum SVR

Without delving into the mathematical details, we can describe the training of an SVR as an optimization problem. However, the SVR problem is not a QUBO problem as, for instance, the variables of their respective objective functions are not binary variables. Still it is possible to use several binary variables to approximate continuous variables in a similar way (but at a smaller scale due to current quantum computer limitations) that classical computers do [13]. Therefore the SVR or SVM optimization problem can be mathematically translated into a very similar QUBO problem as shown by [9] for SVRs and [13], [8] and [3] for SVMs.

Once the SVR training is represented as a QUBO problem it can be solved using a D-wave quantum annealer and the solutions provided by the annealer can be used to reconstruct a trained SVR (in dual formulation), able to make predictions. In [9], several ways of reconstructing the trained SVR from the D-Wave system solutions are proposed. For our work we used all those methods as well as another one consisting of using only the solution corresponding the lowest energy state (or one of them in case there are several that have the same energy) returned by the D-Wave solver.

Via the CoE RAISE project, the Jülich Super Computer Centre provided us with a limited amount of computational time on a D-Wave quantum annealer with Pegasus topology. The Quantum SVR (QSVR) has three different kinds of hyperparameters:

- **SVR hyperparameters:** derived from the mathematical definition of the SVR. Common with Sklearn implementation of SVR.
- **QUBO hyperparameters:** define how the SVR problem is translated to a QUBO problem.
- **Quantum hyperparameters:** specifically related to the quantum annealing process.

A full view of all these QSVR hyperparameters along with a brief definition for each one can be seen in Table 2. Note that the used QSVR is a quantum version of an ϵ -SVR instead of a NuSVR which was used in previous sections. However, even though these two SVR models have slightly different mathematical formulations they can be considered equivalent for a proper choice of their hyperparameters [4].

		HP	Description
		percentage_used	Fraction of the multiple quantum solutions used to reconstruct the SVR
SVR		ϵ	Distance from the actual value with no penalty
		γ	For rbf kernel
		C	Penalty term for missclassifying
QUBO		K	Number of binary variables used to represent a continuous one
		B	Base for the encoding
		k_0	Negative exponent for encoding
		ξ	Penalty term
Quantum		anneal_time	Duration of each annealing cycle
		num_reads	Number of annealing cycles (number of quantum solutions)
		chain_mult	Strength for pairing physical qbits that represent the same variable

Table 2: QSVR Hyperparameters

3.3 Experiments

When first using the QSVR we faced several challenges:

- Only a small fraction of the dataset could be used due to the current limitations of quantum systems. The maximum amount of training points that we could use was 28, however for the experiments presented here we used 20 as we noticed that pushing the number of training points to its limit had a negative impact on the performance. The same happened with the value of K , that determines the precision with which the problem is encoded, as the number of training points, N , and K define the size of the square QUBO matrix which is $2KN$.
- Using only 20 training points made the process more sensitive on the specific training split.
- The performance was very sensitive to the QUBO and Quantum hyperparameters, bad results with negative R^2 could be achieved using SVR parameters that worked well on a classical SVR.
- The results were unstable as the resulting R^2 varied a lot even for the same configuration, sometimes even for the same split.
- The limited quantum computing time available for the project did not allow to perform large-scale hyperparameter optimization.

As only 20 training points were to be used it was decided to reduce the feature vector to have only 13 features coming from the down-sampled learning curve for 25 epochs without any hyperparameter information. Also following the findings for the classical NuSVR we used the QuantileTransformer to preprocess the data. All the experiments performed on the QSVR were done under these conditions.

After several runs of the QSVR, despite the instability of the results, we were able to identify a set of SVR hyperparameters that seemed to perform better than others. More concretely: $\epsilon = 0.02$, $\gamma = 0.1$ and $C = 67.61$. However, some runs were still resulting in low and even negative R^2 values. To study whether this SVR configuration was good or not or if the problem was coming for the QUBO and Quantum hyperparameters we ran 1000 classical SVRs with the

same configuration using a random train/test split each time consisting of 20 training points and 150 test points. The results of these 1000 runs, which can be seen in Figure 11, show that the classical SVR can achieve a good performance with the previously described configuration despite of the low number of training points. Thus, the performance problems of the QSVR when this configuration is used are more likely to come from the QUBO and Quantum hyperparameters.

Figure 11: Resulting R^2 after training and testing a NuSVR on 1000 different splits

With the previous set of SVR hyperparameters fixed the influence of the QUBO hyperparameters such as K , B , k_0 and ξ can be studied using the QSVR but setting the D-Wave sampler (the function that receives the QUBO problem and returns the solutions) to use simulated annealing instead of quantum annealing. As the QUBO problem is still the input for the sampler the translation from SVR to QUBO can be effectively tested without having to worry about the time constraints imposed by the quantum system, the quantum hyperparameters or possible interference effects in the quantum annealing process. Setting $K = 3$, $B = 0.5$, $k_0 = 0.005$ and $\xi = 0.01$ and running the experiment using simulated annealing on 100 different splits we get the results shown in Figure 12. These results are comparable to those obtained on the classical SVR thus the hyperparameters left to be optimized are those related to the quantum machine.

Figure 12: Resulting R^2 after training and testing the Simulated Annealing QSVR on 100 different splits. The different groups of bars on the plot correspond to the different reconstruction techniques as proposed in [9]

Optimizing the quantum hyperparameters of the QSVR like the `anneal_time`, `num_reads` or `chain_mult` can be a tough task given time limit constraints. So in order to choose proper values for these hyperparameters it is interesting to delve a little deeper into how they influence the quantum process. Increasing both the `anneal_time` and `num_reads` can be potentially beneficial but these quantities condition how much quantum computing time is used [6], therefore we cannot arbitrarily increase them. Thus we set `anneal_time` to 20 (its default value from D-Wave) and `num_reads` to 1000 and try to find a good `chain_mult`.

To give a better understanding of what `chain_mult` really is, it is necessary to introduce the concept of chain strength. When embedding the QUBO problem into the physical topology of the quantum system it may not be possible to represent each logical qubit (i.e. each QUBO variable) as a physical qubit. Luckily, this can be solved using more than one physical qubit to represent the same logical qubit. In order to achieve that, the physical qubits have to be “paired”, forcing them to have matching values at all times since they represent the same logical variable. The chain strength value sets how strong the bond is between physical qubits that represent the same logical qubit. The value of the chain strength can be left to be automatically chosen by D-Wave software but this does not always provide good results. D-Wave recommends the maximum absolute value of the QUBO matrix as a good chain strength choice [5].

We use as chain strength either the recommended value multiplied by `chain_mult` like is proposed at [14] or leave the choice to D-wave software. Note that using a chain strength that is too small will result in poor quality solutions as many chains will break during the quantum process. On the other hand, using a too large chain strength value corrupts the optimization problem as the quantum process will evolve trying to keep the bounds between paired physical qubits rather than following the relations between qubits that define the actual optimization problem [5].

During our experiments we observed that for a `chain_mult` value of 1 around 40% of the chains were being broken on average. By increasing the `chain_mult` to 8, 10 and 16 the percentage of broken chains was reduced by more than one order of magnitude. However, for `chain_mult`=16 the resulting R^2 scores were bad, probably due to the optimization getting corrupted. Between the results with `chain_mult`=8 and `chain_mult`=10 the quality of the results was similar with the `chain_mult`=10, although slightly better. Therefore we set `chain_mult` to 10 and ran 10 QSVR on different train/test splits. The results that can be seen in Figure 13 and Table 3 show that we managed to find a configuration for the QSVR able to provide results comparable to those from the classical SVR. In figure 14 the true loss vs the predicted loss for one of the best performing splits can be seen showing that, as was the case with classical SVR, the most serious prediction errors occur for large losses that would be less relevant when using the performance predictor to perform hyperparameter optimization.

method	min	max	mean	median	std
scores norm	0.641861	0.948413	0.865821	0.894811	0.086095
scores softmax	0.760638	0.946151	0.878661	0.893369	0.054855
scores lc norm	0.640308	0.948421	0.865287	0.894510	0.086750
scores lc softmax	0.742472	0.948311	0.880937	0.896780	0.056134
best set of alphas	0.761256	0.946151	0.876103	0.892239	0.056913
simple mean	-0.701135	0.897623	0.658647	0.866834	0.470536
min energy	0.735379	0.915576	0.845504	0.852980	0.057063

Table 3: Summary of R^2 after training and testing the QSVR on 10 different splits. The different methods stand for different reconstruction techniques as proposed in [9]

Figure 13: Resulting R^2 after training and testing the QSVR on an actual QPU on 10 different splits. The different groups of bars on the plot correspond to the different reconstruction techniques as proposed in [9]

Figure 14: True Loss vs predicted loss for one of the best performing QSVR splits. The different sub-plots correspond to the different reconstruction techniques as proposed at [9]

3.4 QSVR combination

As described in previous sections, one of the disadvantages of training an SVR in a quantum device is the strong limitation of the training set size. In an attempt to overcome this limitation we study different techniques to use a larger training set by combining several QSVRs trained on 20 separate samples each. We found that the most successful approach was to split the training set into disjoint subsets of 20 points and train a QSVR for each subset. Then, to make a prediction, all the QSVRs are used separately and the final prediction is calculated as the

average of all the individual predictions.

When designing the algorithm we can benefit from the fact that for each QSVR only a fraction of the total training set is used. Therefore we use the remaining points of the training set to evaluate the R^2 of each QSVR for each reconstruction method. Finally, when making predictions we only use the prediction made by the reconstruction method that reached the highest R^2 during training of each QSVR and finally combine the predictions of all QSVRs by means of a weighted average using their R^2 values weight as weights. The pseudocode of this algorithm can be seen in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: QSVR Combination Algorithm to use larger training sets

```

X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test ← train_test_split(X, y, train_size=80);
num_subsets ← train_size/20;
weights ← array(num_subsets);
method_idx ← array(num_subsets);
models ← list(num_subsets);
for  $i$  in range(num_subsets);                                /* Training Loop */
  do
    idxs ← [20 *  $i$ ...20 * ( $i$  + 1)];
    X_train_i, y_train_i ← X_train[idxs], y_train[idxs];
    X_test_i, y_test_i ← X_train.without(idxs), y_train.without(idxs);
    model ← QSVR();
    model.fit(X_train_i, y_train_i, hyperparameters);
    y_partial_preds ← model.predict(X_test_i);
    for  $pred\_method$  in y_partial_preds do
      | partial_r2[j] = r2_score(pred_method, y_test_i);
    end
    weights[i] ← max(partial_r2.max(), 0);
    method_idx[i] ← partial_r2.argmax();
    models[i] ← model;
  end
y_pred ← array_zeros_like(y_test);
for  $i$  in range(num_subsets);                                /* Prediction Loop */
  do
    | y_pred ← y_pred + weights[i]*models[i].predict(y_test)[method_idx[i]];
  end
y_pred ← y_pred / sum(weights);                                /* Final prediction */

```

To evaluate the QSVR combination technique, we use 80 points for training and 150 points for test and repeat the experiment for 10 random train/test splits. Note that as 80 training points are used, each prediction is made by combining 4 QSVRs trained with 20 points each. The results of this experiment can be seen in Figure 15, they show that the predictions under the combination technique are more stable than those achieved using a single QSVR trained with 20 points. This is interesting as one of the problems faced while using the QSVR was the instability of the results. We tried bigger training sets but the results did not improve. A point of further improvement might be how to calculate the weights in the weighted average that combines the QSVRs as they are likely to have very similar weights under the current method.

R^2 Summary	
Maximum	0.927
Minimum	0.857
Mean	0.899
Median	0.897
Standard Deviation	0.019

Figure 15: Results after running the QSVR combination technique 10 times for 10 different train/test splits using 80 training samples.

4 Conclusions

In this report we evidenced the strong potential of using performance prediction techniques for MLPF, leaving the door open for the use of this technique in later hyperparameter optimization cycles of MLPF. We also showed that, despite the current limitations of quantum computers, it is possible to train a SVR on a quantum annealer achieving prediction performance comparable to those obtained on a classical SVR. Even though quantum computing technologies are still in an early stage and quantum annealers may be more suitable for other types of problems (like graph or combinatorics problems) we showed how quantum technologies can potentially have a place in the classical machine learning design and tuning pipeline.

4.1 Further Work

There are several paths that can be followed to continue the work described in this report. Firstly, implementing a fully working version of a hyperparameter optimization algorithm that makes use of performance prediction techniques that runs on HPC environments is a natural next step. Also, benchmarking such an algorithm and comparing it against current state of the art hyperparameter optimization techniques. Regarding the performance predictor itself, the use of better metrics than the R^2 could be studied as well as how reformulating the problem as a ranking or classification (worth finish training or not) problem could potentially be better than the current regression approach. Regarding the quantum machines, more work could be done to determine which range of classical SVR hyperparameters are suitable for a QSVR. Also, implementing a quantum NuSVR and in general deeper studies of the quantum annealer hyperparameters and how the SVR problem is ported to the quantum machine could be areas where improvement is possible. Finally, other QSVR combination techniques could be developed to achieve more stable or better results.

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